

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

A safe asset in early modern Castile, 1543–1714

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Abstract

This article shows how public offices in the early modern period became investment assets in Castile (Spain). Moreover, it demonstrates that offices fulfilled all the conditions for being viewed as safe assets. In particular, through the combination of qualitative sources with a novel hand-collected database, it shows that offices did not suffer from adverse selection, were traded in liquid secondary markets, and increased their value during periods of economic distress. This research is a pioneer in revealing the existence in early modern times of a haven asset, other than coins and public debt, and showing at the same time the private financial uses of offices.

KEYWORDS

Augmented mean group model, early modern finance, safe assets, venality

The Great Recession raised new economic questions, one of them concerning the role that safe assets play in the financial system. However, despite the progress of research in this field in the last fifteen years,¹ we still know little about these assets in the past. Only Gorton,² who roughly analyses the history of haven assets, and Schmelzing,³ who studies the evolution of European safe public debt, deal with this as a historical topic.

This paper sheds new light on the field by analysing how local offices became haven assets. In doing so, the research closes the existing gap in Spanish literature on the financial uses and

¹ Caballero and Farhi, ‘The safety trap’; He, Krishnamurthy, and Milbradt, ‘What makes US government bonds safe assets?’; Holmstrom, ‘Understanding the role of debt’.

² Gorton, ‘The history and economics of safe assets’.

³ Schmelzing, ‘Eight centuries of global real interest rates’.

properties of offices. Simultaneously, employing novel techniques to analyse in-depth the behaviour of safe assets, it demonstrates that they existed in preindustrial economies, particularly in societies like Castile, where markets were seriously distorted.

An office was a license to be a royal agent. During the sixteenth century these licenses were sold all around the world.⁴ The act of selling them was called venality. It is not new to compare offices with financial assets, as contemporaries in particular did. For instance, offices ‘were regarded as one of the four elements in a family’s estate – the others being land, houses, and rentes’.⁵ Likewise, according to Pierre Goubert: ‘a good story of offices would not know how to separate itself in the least degree from a sound history of prices, wealth, investments, income, and money’.⁶ Even so, several questions are still unanswered about their financial role for families in Castile, mainly because research has focused on its social, fiscal, and political aspects. The literature on venality, for example, typically highlights that the purchase of aldermanship led to upward social mobility,⁷ but it is still doubtful whether these offices yielded substantial economic profits beyond bribes and the rewards from the king.

To provide an appropriate response, in this article I build the most comprehensive database so far of the venal Castilian system. It contains about 4157 resignations and 1910 sales of four types of office (aldermen, solicitors, notaries, and different sorts of clerk) in eight major Castilian cities over the period between 1543 and 1714. Data collection is based essentially on the original documents of the Council of Finance and the Chamber of Castile, which recorded transactions of offices, most notably the Books of Offices from *Contaduría de la Razón* and files of resignations of the Chamber.⁸

By exploiting this dataset, I find that offices, thanks to a contractual innovation, could be leased, though this was formally prohibited. This innovation was the repurchasing agreement (in Spanish *pacto de retroventa*). Office owners were able to transform lease operations into sale transactions that had been legal since 1543–5. Furthermore, the combination of repurchasing agreements, offices, and *censos* (long-term loans) allowed investors to create sophisticated financial vehicles. All these innovations increased office returns and allowed anyone, regardless of skill and condition, to participate in the market by holding an office.

Next, I ask whether offices satisfied the criteria of safe assets, namely, no adverse selection, liquidity, and higher value as the economy weakened. In particular, I show that simplicity, common-knowledge features, no depreciation, stable yields, and some screening controls prevented offices from suffering from adverse selection. Moreover, a highly developed secondary market made these assets quite liquid. As a final point, by using an augmented mean group model, I find that office prices had a significant, negative relationship with GDP per capita, and a positive relationship with public debt risk. This demonstrates that investors increased their demand for these assets when adverse economic events occurred. I hence conclude that venal offices fulfilled all the requirements to be considered safe assets.

In addition to the newly created database, this article makes a number of contributions that relate to the literature in financial and economic history. First, it contributes to the financial literature by being, to the best of my knowledge, the first paper to analyse the emergence of a safe asset

⁴ Swart, *Sale of offices*.

⁵ Giesey, ‘State-building in early modern France’, p. 200.

⁶ *Ibid.*, p. 205.

⁷ Hernández Benítez, ‘Ayuntamientos urbanos, trampolines sociales’.

⁸ All the sources are summarized in [table A3](#) in the appendix.

in the pre-industrial period that is different from bonds or precious metals.⁹ Novel dynamic panel data methodologies are moreover applied to capture the specific properties of haven assets.¹⁰ Second, it contributes to the literature on venality by taking a financial approach to explore Castilian offices and showing how these assets became private financial products.¹¹ Finally, it relates to the literature on economic institutions. It connects with research that studies how institutions affect financial development.¹² More specifically, the article shows a case study in which the Spanish Crown successfully defined the property rights of an asset, thus conferring desirable financial attributes on it (i.e. safety).¹³

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. After the introduction, I summarize the historical context, especially focusing on the haven assets and venality in Castile. Then, section II describes the database and sources in detail. Section III analyses how offices became financial investments and what sort of transactions were carried out. I lastly test whether offices satisfied all the safe asset properties in section IV. A final section offers a brief conclusion.

I | SAFE ASSETS AND VENALITY IN EARLY MODERN CASTILE

The sixteenth century was a period of economic growth in Castile. Despite some structural problems, Castilian GDP per capita was higher than in most European kingdoms in 1500, and grew even faster throughout the following century.¹⁴ Economic growth went hand in hand with financial development.¹⁵ A good example is the emergence of two key safe assets in early modern Europe, *real de a ocho* (silver coin) and *juros* (long-term public debt).

A safe asset is defined as ‘an asset that can be used to transact without fear of adverse selection’.¹⁶ This short definition captures the two most important attributes of these instruments. On the one hand, it points out the information insensitivity that comes from simplicity and absence of the adverse selection. On the other hand, it captures liquidity or ‘moneyness’.¹⁷ Both qualities convert these assets into suitable store of value in an economic crisis.¹⁸ Moreover, as explained below, these characteristics were present in Castilian bonds and precious metal coins.

The *real de a ocho* is the most recognized silver coin of Castile. During the seventeenth century, it turned out to be a quasi-international reserve. Indeed, European bullion exports to Asia were made up of 50 per cent Spanish minting.¹⁹ This fact has its root in the responsible

⁹ Gorton, ‘The history and economics of safe assets’; Schmelzing, ‘Eight centuries of global real interest rates’.

¹⁰ Eberhardt, Helmers, and Strauss, ‘Do spillovers matter’; Eberhardt and Teal, ‘Econometrics for grumblers’.

¹¹ Tomás y Valiente, *Gobierno e Instituciones*; Domínguez Ortiz, ‘La venta de cargos y oficios públicos en Castilla’; Marcos Martín, ‘Las caras de la venalidad’; Andújar Castillo and Ponce Leiva, *Mérito, venalidad y corrupción*; Hernández Benítez, ‘Y después de las ventas de oficios ¿qué?’; Hernández Benítez, ‘Cuando el poder se vende’.

¹² Beck, Demircug-Kunt, and Levine, ‘Law and finance’; La Porta et al., ‘Law and finance’; North, *Institutions, institutional change*.

¹³ Álvarez-Nogal, ‘Incentivos económicos y derechos de propiedad’; Grafe and Irigoien, ‘A stakeholder empire’.

¹⁴ Álvarez-Nogal and Prados de la Escosura, ‘The decline of Spain’, p. 357; Yun-Casalilla, ‘Proposals to quantify long-term performance’.

¹⁵ Ruiz Martín, *La banca en España hasta 1782*; Marcos Martín, *España en los siglos XVI, XVII y XVIII*.

¹⁶ Gorton, ‘The history and economics of safe assets’, p. 547.

¹⁷ ‘Moneyness’ is implicit in the expression of ‘can be used to transact’.

¹⁸ Caballero, Farhi, and Gourinchas, ‘The safe assets shortage conundrum’.

¹⁹ Motomura, ‘New data on minting’, p. 340.

monetary policy initiated by the Catholic Kings in 1497, and maintained by Charles V (1517–56) and Philip II (1556–98) of Spain.²⁰ Even though the seventeenth century brought about negligent management practices (i.e. debasement and re-stamping were used to meet budget deficits), these policies concerned only copper coins (*vellón*). This was due to differences in the currency markets. While the Castilian Crown enjoyed a monopoly in *vellón* money, gold and silver coins competed in international markets where every crown tried to increase its market share in minting services.²¹ Spanish monarchs, therefore, made rational decisions and merely altered the value of copper coins, guaranteeing the reputation and competitiveness of their silver pieces.

As a consequence, the *vellón* showed high inflation rates, and people started to hoard silver to protect their wealth from inflation.²² Copper money then expelled other currencies from circulation as Gresham's law predicts, and a silver premium, which partly mirrors the overprice paid for safety, emerged from 1603 onwards.²³ Contemporary testimonies and statistical evidence clearly indicate that silver reals were used as a safe asset and inflation hedge during this century.²⁴ Monetary chaos was not addressed until 1680–6 when a severe deflationary policy was undertaken, and manipulation of copper coins ended.²⁵

Besides precious metals, Castile also counted on another much-appreciated haven asset, the *juros*. Castile was the first kingdom with a huge nationwide domestic public debt.²⁶ During the reigns of Charles V and Philip II, consolidated *juros* multiplied by more than 26-fold (figure 1).

Successful financial management had much to do with the strong commitment mechanisms of *juros* that significantly increased their security. Similar to the bonds of Italian city-states,²⁷ interest payments of Castilian *juros* were backed by specific taxes. Additionally, most bonds were issued by the Crown but serviced by the cities, limiting moral hazard problems.²⁸ This mechanism, combined with a liquid secondary market,²⁹ converted them into the 'proverbial risk-free, marketable asset of the day', as Schmelzing labelled Italian debt in the fifteenth century.³⁰

In spite of several suspensions of payments being enacted during Philip II's reign, credibility of *juros* remained almost unaffected, as bond investors did not suffer from large losses during the three initial suspensions declared in 1556, 1560, and 1575.³¹ Accordingly, *juros*' interest rates steadily declined. Figure 2 indeed shows that a convenience yield (i.e. the spread between the yield of a safe asset, the *juros*, and the yield of a non-risk-free asset, the global rate of sovereign

²⁰ Santiago Fernández, 'Moneda y fiscalidad en Castilla durante el siglo XVI'.

²¹ Motomura, 'The best and worst of currencies'.

²² Hamilton, *War and prices in Spain*; Hamilton, *American treasure and the price revolution*.

²³ The ratio of payments in *vellón* to silver was 95% between 1650 and 1680. The silver premium peaked in the 1670s, exceeding 300% (Hamilton, *War and prices in Spain*).

²⁴ Font de Villanueva, 'La estabilización monetaria de 1680–1686'; Serrano Mangas, *Vellón y metales preciosos en la corte*; García de Paso, 'La política monetaria castellana de los siglos XVI y XVII'.

²⁵ Font de Villanueva, 'La estabilización monetaria de 1680–1686'.

²⁶ Álvarez-Nogal and Chamley, 'Debt policy under constraints', p. 192.

²⁷ Fratianni and Spinelli, 'Italian city-states and financial evolution'.

²⁸ Some sorts of *juros* were backed by taxes directly managed by the Crown. These bonds, which represented a minor fraction, did not fulfil the second condition (I thank an anonymous referee for this helpful clarification).

²⁹ Alonso García and Caselli, 'Government debts and financial markets in Castile', p. 40.

³⁰ Schmelzing, 'Eight centuries of global real interest rates', p. 21.

³¹ Álvarez-Nogal, 'Oferta y demanda de deuda pública en Castilla'; Drelichman and Voth, 'The sustainable debts of Philip II'.

FIGURE 1 Consolidated Castilian public debt (*juros*) in millions of current ducats, 1504–98. *Source:* Marcos Martín, ‘¿Fue la fiscalidad regia un factor de crisis en Castilla del siglo XVII?’, p. 232.

FIGURE 2 Nominal interest rate of *juros* and global sovereign rate, 1505–98. *Notes:* Data shared by Francisco Comín and collected from Marcos Martín, ‘La deuda pública de la Corona de Castilla’, p. 33; Marcos Martín, ‘Deuda pública, mercado crediticio y actividad económica’; De Carlos Morales, ‘Los juros y el endeudamiento de la Real Hacienda’; Artola Gallego, *La Hacienda del Antiguo Régimen*, pp. 86–7; Álvarez-Nogal, ‘La rentabilidad de los juros’. *Source:* Comín, *La crisis de la deuda soberana en España*, p. 74, and Schmelzing ‘Eight centuries of global real interest rates’.

debt)³² appeared since the 1550s. This spread exceeded 5 per cent in the 1560s, and was close to 3 per cent by the late sixteenth century.

Nevertheless, from the 1590s onwards this outstanding performance rapidly deteriorated. Ruiz Martín points out that Genoese bankers had begun to be more cautious by 1586. Uncertainty peaked in the period 1593–5 before the suspension of payments.³³ During this decade, Castile faced a challenging crisis. Several economic issues had arisen in the previous years, such as the reduction of wool exports,³⁴ low productivity linked to large inflows of precious metals that caused a Dutch disease,³⁵ and an increasingly serious burden of taxation.³⁶ Moreover, in the 1590s, the combination of bad harvests, an outbreak of plague,³⁷ and the suspension of payments of 1596–8 triggered the worst economic and financial crisis of the century, giving rise to the ‘general crisis’ of Castile.³⁸

In these circumstances, an ordinary tax increase to solve the critical situation of public finance by raising the ceiling on bond issues was impossible. In particular, after the resolution agreement of 1597, interest on *juros* still accounted for 94.73 per cent of overall royal ordinary incomes.³⁹ A slight reduction of tax collected threatened the servicing of outstanding *juros* so that the Crown had to declare a new suspension in 1607. Schmelzing considers that debt primacy moved from Castile to the Dutch financial centre at this moment in time.⁴⁰

After a temporary amelioration in the 1610s, when the Genoese bankers took over debt management through the *Diputación del Medio General* and Castile signed the Twelve Years Truce with the Dutch rebels,⁴¹ the worst time for *juros* came in the 1620s. As the silver premium rose, Philip III decided to stop paying the interest on *juros* in silver coin. Such a policy damaged *juros*-holders since inflation of copper money was high. Philip IV subsequently seized interest payments in 1625, 1629, and every year from 1634 onwards with the creation of the *media annata de juros*.⁴² Two more suspensions took place in 1627 and 1647. As a result, *juros* were no longer in great demand, and interest payments were described as ‘difficult, costly and belated payback’.⁴³

All these shortcomings not only affected the profitability of *juros* but also eroded their properties as secure assets. A haven asset must be information insensitive; in other words, it has to fulfil the non-question asked property.⁴⁴ This holds true if assets are easy to understand, and do not suffer from adverse selection. Thus, nobody is willing to pay for information to better estimate the probability of default. The amount of money that someone is willing to pay for this

³² Gorton, ‘The history and economics of safe assets’.

³³ Ruiz Martín, *La banca en España hasta 1782*, pp. 49–51.

³⁴ Casado Alonso and Tena Junguito, ‘¿Crisis comerciales en la historia de España?’; Bilbao and Fernández de Pinedo, ‘Exportación de lanas, trashumancia y ocupación del espacio en Castilla’.

³⁵ Drelichman, ‘The curse of Moctezuma’.

³⁶ Ruiz Martín, ‘Las finanzas españolas’; Ulloa, *La hacienda real de Castilla*.

³⁷ Pérez Moreda and Collantes Gutiérrez, ‘Crisis demográficas del pasado’; Vincent, ‘La peste Atlántica de 1596–1602’.

³⁸ Yun-Casalilla, ‘Estado y estructuras sociales en Castilla’.

³⁹ De Carlos Morales, ‘El precio del dinero dinástico’, p. 148.

⁴⁰ Schmelzing, ‘Eight centuries of global real interest rates’, p. 23.

⁴¹ Gelabert, *La bolsa del rey*.

⁴² *Media annata de juros* was a tax levied on between one-fifth and a half of *juros* interest payments. (Álvarez-Nogal, ‘Oferta y demanda de deuda pública en Castilla’, pp. 33–4).

⁴³ *Ibid.*, p. 49.

⁴⁴ Holmstrom, ‘Understanding the role of debt’.

information is called information acquisition sensitivity (IAS).⁴⁵ The fundamentals of *juros* were probably not simple since they involved sophisticated taxes as collateral. In fact, some investors (e.g. Genoese bankers) employed expert agents in Madrid who advised them and managed rents on their behalf.⁴⁶ Although *juros* could hence generate some information asymmetries since they carried different default probability, IAS was probably very low during the sixteenth century because interests were almost systematically serviced.⁴⁷ The suspension of payments in 1596, however, greatly increased IAS. Since then, some scholars have highlighted that investors in *juros* tried to acquire privileged information from local treasurers to find out how far a tax was being exploited.⁴⁸ In addition, after the 1590s Genoese bankers and Castilian investors started to use real estate and offices as collateral, probably feeling safer with them than with *juros*.⁴⁹ These facts best exemplify the increase in IAS after the suspension.

In parallel with the rise and fall of *juros*, Castile saw the creation of another relevant institution, that is, the venal system. Castilian venality has its roots in the late Middle Ages when John II (1405–55) of Castile introduced the canon law *resignatio in favorem* in the kingdom.⁵⁰ This rule allowed local officers to designate successors for their posts as long as they fulfilled certain conditions (e.g. not being paid in return). Despite the explicit prohibition of pecuniary compensation, the law turned out to be an effective tool for selling offices under the counter and making them hereditary, as happened in France.⁵¹ This process is known as the ‘patrimonialization’ of offices, in which they stopped being de facto part of royal prerogatives to turn into individual patrimonies.⁵²

Given the repeated complaints in the Castilian parliament about concealed sales, Isabella I (1479–1504) increased the restrictions over resignations. One of the foremost measures was the 62nd rule of the *Cortes de Toledo* (1480), which established that an officer had to live at least 20 days after the resignation date to validate the designation (hereafter the 20-day rule). Otherwise the office would return to the Crown and could be ‘consumed’ (i.e. extinguished).⁵³ These controls, however, gradually relaxed with Charles V’s administration until 1543, when a turning point occurred.

After seeing the royal short-term financial needs skyrocket,⁵⁴ Prince Philip, who had been appointed regent of Castile in May 1543, decided to start selling offices to meet his financial commitments. This ushered in large-scale sales of offices by the Crown. The amounts collected in cities represented in the *Cortes* (Castilian Parliament) reached 36 per cent of the annual *alcabalas*

⁴⁵ Gorton, ‘The history and economics of safe assets’.

⁴⁶ Maréchaux, ‘Business organisation in the Mediterranean Sea’, p. 19.

⁴⁷ Drelichman and Voth, *Lending to the borrower from hell*, p. 22.

⁴⁸ Álvarez-Nogal, ‘Oferta y demanda de deuda pública en Castilla’, p. 45; Comín, *La crisis de la deuda soberana en España*, p. 73.

⁴⁹ Ruiz Martín, *La banca en España hasta 1782*, p. 52.

⁵⁰ Tomás y Valiente, *La venta de oficios en Indias*, p. 37.

⁵¹ Mousnier, *La vénalité des offices sous Henri IV et Louis XIII*.

⁵² Tomás y Valiente, ‘Origen bajomedieval de la patrimonialización’; Marcos Martín, ‘Las caras de la venalidad’, pp. 85–90; Hernández Benítez, ‘Cuando el poder se vende’, pp. 75–81; Jiménez Estrella, ‘El precio de las almenas’, p. 19.

⁵³ Fortea Pérez, ‘El debate en torno a la venta de oficios concejiles’.

⁵⁴ *Asientos* (short-term loans) contracted increased by 407% between 1542 and 1543 (Carande, *Carlos V y sus banqueros*, pp. 28–31).

and *tercias* collection.⁵⁵ Successful collection laid the foundation for the institutionalization process, through which the property rights of offices were progressively defined, probably seeking to maximize the prices in future sales.⁵⁶ In 1545, the *facultad de renunciación* (license of resignation) broke ground in this process. By purchasing this license, office holders were able to remove most legal restrictions on resignations (e.g. the 20-day rule, or using the office to pay off a debt).⁵⁷

Over the following decades, the venal system developed further. Primary sales, which initially involved only three sorts of office (aldermen, juries, and notaries of the number) in just a few cities, expanded to reach even the smallest villages throughout Castile and involved more and more varied offices.⁵⁸ Alongside the expansion, venality also increased in complexity. Even though the laws that banned the sale of offices lingered in the Castilian code (*Nova Recopilación*, 1567), they were nullified while the licenses of resignation proliferated. Castillo de Bobadilla, an influential jurist at the time, highlighted it in 1597, when he wrote that it would be preferable to erase such rules from the *Nova Recopilación* since they were ‘not enforced anymore ... because of the wits of some, and the great obligations and needs of His Majesty’.⁵⁹ It must be emphasized that licenses of resignation were even sold *ex post* to the relatives of office owners who had violated the 20-day rule. The ‘consumption’ of offices hence became easily avoidable by simply paying the Crown. In fact, no office was ‘consumed’ from the 1580s onwards in the cities which this article analyses.⁶⁰

The institutionalization process thus implied a *de facto* legalization of the market for offices. Theoretically, this should not only have increased sales in the market by abrogating penalties but should also have reduced transaction costs and limited information asymmetries by making contracts enforceable.⁶¹ Under incomplete contracts, the impossibility of third party verification results in underinvestment and moral hazard.⁶² However, Philip II’s policies avoided these problems by eliminating the legal loophole that had resulted from the introduction of *resignatio in favorem*, as Castillo de Bobadilla points out.

The definition of property rights concluded with the sale of the *facultad de perpetuación* (license of perpetuation) in the early seventeenth century.⁶³ Perpetuations, as they came to be called, embedded most of the rights that could be acquired separately from the Crown (e.g. license of

⁵⁵ *Alcabalas* and *tercias* were the most relevant Castilian royal tax in the sixteenth century. Despite being a sales tax, it was often managed as a direct tax in several cities (Gómez-Blanco, ‘When safety becomes risky’, pp. 58–9; and Artola Gallego, ‘La Hacienda del Antiguo Régimen’).

⁵⁶ *Ibid.*, pp. 59–62.

⁵⁷ Archivo General de Simancas (AGS), Cámara de Castilla (CCA), Diversos (DIV), file 47-33.1.

⁵⁸ Resignations existed at least in 180 different types of urban office and 67 rural. However, the sales concentrated on the local level of Castilian administration. The Crown refused to sell offices with judicial powers such as *corregidores* or offices of *Consejos*. (Gómez-Blanco, ‘When safety becomes risky’).

⁵⁹ Castillo de Bobadilla, *Política para corregidores*, p. 231.

⁶⁰ Between 1571 and 1602, the Crown also authorized city councils to buy back some sorts of office. Repurchased offices by the city council were sometimes placed out of the market since the officers began to be appointed by their own council after the buyback. This process came to be called ‘consumption’ as well. However, these authorizations only affected the offices from small-size towns and certain city offices such as *fieles ejecutores* (major market inspectors). Moreover, the ownership rights were always enforced because the city hall had to pay back to the office owner. The initial investment was hence never at risk (Gómez-Blanco, ‘When safety becomes risky’, pp. 62–3; Marcos Martín, ‘Las caras de la venalidad’, p. 96).

⁶¹ Aghion and Holden, ‘Incomplete contracts and the theory of the firm’, p. 185; Williamson, ‘Transaction-cost economics’.

⁶² Grossman and Hart, ‘The costs and benefits of ownership’.

⁶³ Marcos Martín, ‘Las ventas de oficios en Castilla’, pp. 31–2.

resignation, to entail the office, or designate a deputy) in exchange for a one-time payment.⁶⁴ As a result, the offices permanently turned into legal private assets. Venality then expanded to a greater extent in the American colonies⁶⁵ and to other sorts of offices, such as the military ones.⁶⁶ The venal system became less relevant over the eighteenth century, but offices were still sold up to 1822, when the liberal government abolished the whole system.⁶⁷

II | SOURCES AND DATABASE

In spite of the extensive literature on Castilian venality, quantitative secondary evidence is in general scarce and fragmented. Except for the studies of Cuartas, Marcos, and Hernández, who covered different types of offices throughout Castile,⁶⁸ quantification exercises have focused on specific offices (most usually aldermen) and/or a city or small region.⁶⁹ Moreover, this literature mostly considers primary sales.

The thorough research of office financial properties hence requires a representative sample of both primary and secondary markets in Castile to be built. To do so, the original books and files of the two royal councils in charge of the venal system (i.e. the Council of Finance and the Chamber of Castile) have been extensively analysed. Table A3 in the appendix summarizes the sources.

For the primary market, the most relevant documents are the *Libros de Oficios* (Books of Offices) and files of the *Contaduría de la Razón*, as well as the books of information on offices of the Chamber of Castile. The *Contaduría de la Razón* was the institution commissioned to register the royal revenues from offices. Despite being founded on 25 May 1554, the accountant Francisco de Almaguer, lieutenant of the *Contador Mayor de Hacienda* (Chief Accountant of the Council of Finance), in 1543 decided on his own to begin keeping ledgers for the sales of offices,⁷⁰ which again highlights this year as the start of the institutionalization process. Accordingly, these are the reference books to track primary sales. At the same time, the Chamber, which had the power to control resignations and issue office titles, managed its own books which gathered the writs, decrees, sales, and licenses of offices. All the documents of the *Contaduría de la Razón* and Chamber of Castile are kept in different sections of the *Archivo General de Simancas* (AGS) and *Archivo Histórico Nacional* (AHN) – see table A3.

Regarding the secondary market, the most relevant source by far consists of the resignation files. This was due to the fact that any incumbent officer was obliged to inform the Chamber through a resignation deed when designating a new officer (by a sale, appointment, succession, etc.). When

⁶⁴ This payment was initially to be fixed at one-third of the market value of the office. Nonetheless, the Crown sold the licenses at approximately 15% of the office market value, reducing this amount even more over the years. (Gómez-Blanco, 'When safety becomes risky', p. 163).

⁶⁵ Tomás y Valiente, *La venta de oficios en Indias*; Andújar Castillo, 'El mercado de venta de cargos de Indias'.

⁶⁶ Andújar Castillo, 'Guerra, venalidad y asientos de soldados'.

⁶⁷ Hernández Benítez, 'Venalidad de oficios municipales'; Tomás y Valiente, *Gobierno e instituciones*.

⁶⁸ Cuartas Rivero, 'La venta de oficios públicos'; Marcos Martín, 'Las caras de la venalidad'; Marcos Martín, 'Las ventas de oficios en Castilla'; Hernández Benítez, 'Venalidad de oficios municipales'.

⁶⁹ Fernández Martín, 'Venalidad de oficios'; Cabañas García, 'Los regidores de la ciudad de Burgos'; Jiménez Estrella, 'El precio de las almenas'; Casey, *Familia, poder y comunidad*; Guerrero Mayllo, *El gobierno municipal*; Domínguez Guerrero, *Las escribanías públicas del alfoz*; Faya Díaz, 'Gobierno municipal'; Ocaña Cuadros, 'Las regidurías acrecentadas'; Cuesta Martínez, *Oficios públicos y sociedad*; Gutiérrez Alonso, *Estudio sobre la decadencia de Castilla*.

⁷⁰ Hernández Esteve, 'Las contadurías de libros de la Contaduría Mayor de Hacienda', p. 105.

the documents were validated, the Chamber would issue a new title. The content and representativeness of these files varies over the years.⁷¹ Before the 1570s, failing to report resignations was not uncommon. The Crown hence began from 1579 onwards to increase its monitoring under penalty of office loss.⁷² Increasingly controls were implemented which rendered the misreporting of resignation deeds practically negligible, especially when in 1631 resignations started to be taxed with the creation of the *media annata de mercedes*.⁷³ Resignation deeds sometimes included additional information, such as the reasons for renouncing or the sale price. However, more often than not it simply named the old and new officers, making it hard to tell whether the resignation had been a sale, a rental, or a free appointment. Files, by contrast, became more detailed from the 1630s to 1640s onwards, due to the proliferation of perpetuities and the above-mentioned *media annata de mercedes*. Since then, office-holders started to add other documents to the resignation files, such as purchase-and-sale agreements and certificates of debts for which the offices served as collateral. All the files of resignations are preserved in the AGS (CCA, *Renuncias, legajos* from 2295 to 2552) and AHN (CON, *legajos* from 13 745 to 13 806). In total, 412 files (about 41 200 pages) and 103 books have been analysed for the present study. Given the quantity of these sources, the data collection process focused on some specific cities and offices.

Because the earliest primary sales affected only a handful of charges in medium and large cities, the potential candidates were limited. In particular, the offices sold on a large scale in the 1540s were those of *regidores-veinticuatro* (aldermen), *escribanos del número* (notaries of the number), *jurados* (juries), and *escribanos del ayuntamiento* (clerks of the city hall). Among them, juries were excluded since they existed only in a few cities (some Andalusian cities and Toledo). The offices of *alférez mayor* (standard bearer) and *alcaide de fortaleza* (governor of fortress) began to be traded in the 1550s, but they were not recorded because these offices represented small markets, which considerably reduced the chance of finding enough transactions (there was usually one standard bearer per city, and fortresses were scarce). In the early 1560s, *procuradores del número* (solicitors), together with aldermen and notaries, began to occupy most of the offices that came on the market. They are hence included in the sample. Finally, *escribanos* (clerks) of other sorts were also added because distinctive insights can be drawn from them. Most notable among these were the *escribanos de cámara y crimen* (law court clerks) and *escribanos de provincia* (provincial clerks-notaries), which allow us to analyse offices that belonged to a royal institution, such as *Chancillería* or *Audiencia* (appeals courts of the kingdom), and not strictly local ones.

In sum, the sample mostly comprises aldermen, notaries of the number, solicitors, clerks of the city hall and law court, and provincial notaries. Table 1 briefly sets out their functions and salaries. As shown, the sample is highly heterogeneous. The offices had a wide range of powers and functions: political (aldermen), administrative (clerks), or judicial (solicitors). Salaries were also diverse. Even though most Castilian offices had mixed salaries (fixed and variable pay), the offices in the sample range from purely variable pay (notaries) to mixed salaries with low fixed pay (aldermen) or high fixed pay (clerks of city hall).

As with the selection of offices, the search for locations aimed for the highest representativeness. The cities included in the sample are Burgos, Córdoba, Granada, Madrid,⁷⁴ Málaga, Seville, Valladolid, and Zamora. As displayed in table 2, all the major regions of Castile are represented

⁷¹ Gómez-Blanco, '¿Venalidad o venalidades?'

⁷² AGS, CCA, CON, files 13-2 (Granada) and 34 (Valladolid).

⁷³ *Media annata de mercedes* was a tax on resignations of offices, levying half of the office yearly returns estimated at 5% (AHN, CON, book 545).

⁷⁴ Evidence about the aldermen from Madrid was collected by Mauro Hernández, who generously shared the data.

TABLE 1 Description of functions and salaries of offices analysed.

	Functions	Salary	First primary sale
<i>Regidor</i> or <i>veinticuatro</i> (alderman)	Main functions involved administrative, commercial, economic, and security policies at the city level; <i>regidores</i> had voice and vote and led commissions in the city council. This office provided high status due to its responsibilities and association with nobility.	The <i>regidor's</i> fixed wage was low, for example, about 55 reals/year in Segovia. However, this officer could obtain high profits from participating in commissions at city hall, bribes, and graces from the king, especially when appointed <i>procurador de Cortes</i> (member of the parliament), or he lent special services to the monarch.	1543
<i>Escribano del ayuntamiento</i> (clerk of city hall)	<i>Escribano del ayuntamiento</i> was the chief clerk at city hall. His main responsibility was to keep meeting records and manage any other official document originating in the city council, such as public contracts and regulations.	His remuneration depended on the number of meetings held at the city hall and deeds written. For instance, an <i>escribano del ayuntamiento</i> in Seville received 5 reals/meeting and 2.5 extra reals if a meeting was on a holiday. This assured him at least 500 reals a year. This can be considered as a semifixed salary. Overall final salary was about 2200 (northern cities) or 6600 reals per year (Andalusian cities). However, some clerks reached up to 11 000 reals (e.g. Málaga or Seville).	1549
<i>Escribano del número</i> (notary)	This officer was a standard notary in the early modern period. He usually worked in a city's main square or at his own home/office. Every official deed had to be validated by a signature from an <i>escribano del número</i> or a higher-rank <i>escribano</i> to be formally legal.	This officer received a fee by deed and extra pages (1 real/deed plus half a real per extra page). Total salary depended on deeds written. It was often high (e.g. over 3300 reals/year in Granada), although it relied on the notary's effort and the activity level of the town.	1544

(Continues)

TABLE 1 (Continued)

	Functions	Salary	First primary sale
<i>Procurador del número</i> (solicitor)	The <i>procurador del número</i> was an official lawyer in civil, criminal, and religious proceedings.	His salary had a low fixed portion (approximately, 165 reals/year), and a variable payment, which depended on the trials in which he participated (no information on variable pay has been found).	1562
<i>Escribano de cámara</i> (law court clerk)	The <i>escribano de cámara</i> was a major clerk and notary at Castilian appeals courts (<i>Chancillerías</i> in Granada and Valladolid, and <i>Audiencia</i> in Seville). His main responsibility was to register and attest proceedings.	Salary depended on the number of pages of proceedings written and signed. The range of salaries also depended on the seniority of the officer, but all wages were high, ranging from 3300 to 8800 reals per year.	1594
<i>Escribano de provincia</i> (provincial notary)	The <i>escribano de provincia</i> was a notary that acted at the <i>Chancillería</i> . His main responsibility was to write deeds giving official attestation of proceedings which occurred near the <i>Chancillería</i> .	Salary depended on the number of deeds produced. Average salaries ranged from 2200 (Valladolid) to 6600 reals (Seville) per year. No information about the fixed portion of the salary has been found.	1594

Source: Alderman (Mosácula María, 'Los regidores municipales de Segovia'), clerk of city hall (AGS, DGT Inventario 24, file 322 and file 20), notary of the number (AGS, CCA, CON, file 20; AGS, CCA, LEG, file 2347; Domínguez Guerrero, *Las escribanías públicas del alfoz*), solicitor (AGS, CCA, CON, file 20), legal court clerk (AGS, CCA, CON, file 30; AGS, CCA, REL, file 20), and provincial clerk (AGS, CCA, CON, file 34; and Arroyal Espigares, 'Nómina de notarios, escribanos y oficiales de pluma en Andalucía').

(i.e. Old Castile, New Castile, and Andalusia). Moreover, these places cover a wide spectrum of sizes. For instance, Zamora and Málaga were small cities with fewer than 10 000 inhabitants, while Seville and Madrid, by contrast, were the largest cities of the kingdom (approximately 90 000 inhabitants each in 1591). The number of offices, which is closely related to the size of the location, widely varies as well. Finally, these cities were to some extent different in political terms. Málaga is included because it was a city without voting rights in the parliament. Additionally, some locations had influential institutions that could benefit some of its office-holders, while others did not (e.g. the *Corte* in Madrid, *Casa de la Contratación* in Seville, and *Chancillerías* in Granada and Valladolid).

Based on this selection, the resulting database contains 1910 sales, 4157 resignations, and 315 leases that took place between 1543 and 1714. This is by far the most comprehensive dataset of Castilian venal offices to date. Among the sales, 547 were made in the primary market (29 per cent) and 1363 in the secondary (71 per cent).

TABLE 2 Main characteristics of selected cities.

	Region	Population in 1591	Aldermen in 1581	Solicitors in 1581	Notaries of the number in 1581	Vote at Cortes	Major royal institutions
Burgos	Old Castile	10 660	22	16	28	Yes	<i>Consulado del Mar</i> (Consulate of the Sea)
Córdoba	Andalusia	40 000	49	26	36	Yes	
Granada	Andalusia	32 800	41	48	27	Yes	<i>Chancillería</i> (southern Castilian appeals court)
Madrid	New Castile	90 000	28	57	21	Yes	<i>Corte</i> (Royal Court) and <i>Consejos</i> (royal councils)
Málaga	Andalusia	9440	28	21	20	No	
Seville	Andalusia	92 664	57	24	22	Yes	<i>Audiencia</i> (appeals court), and <i>Casa de la Contratación</i> (American trade monopoly)
Valladolid	Old Castile	40 000	30	30	30	Yes	<i>Chancillería</i> (northern Castilian appeals court)
Zamora	Old Castile	6780	24	11	23	Yes	

Note: Old Castile covered the northern region of the kingdom of Castile, New Castile lay in central and mid-south, and Andalusia covered the south of Castile. Source: Author's database (see section II) and Fortea Pérez, 'Las ciudades de la Corona de Castilla en el Antiguo Régimen'.

Note that all secondary sales were also resignations since it was mandatory to submit the resignation deed to sign in the new tenancy. The database, however, includes 2794 resignations for which no corresponding purchase-and-sale agreement or price information was found. This is partly because some of the resignations were not sales but free appointments (transfers between relatives, successions, dowries, etc.). Still, it also reveals the fact that office-holders often failed to note the sale details, especially before the 1630s, as discussed above. Bearing in mind that free appointments or donations between non-relatives should have been unusual, information on family ties in these resignations was collected. Only 922 (33 per cent) of these resignations (without price) involved relatives. Consequently, most of the rest (1872 or 67 per cent) were probably misreported sales. During the period analysed, total sales were possibly around 3782. The database then provides complete information to do with half or more of all potential sales (51 per cent).

The prices of all the sales (in current reals) are displayed in figures A1 and A2 in the appendix. These figures show a relatively equitable distribution of sales over the years, although for the reasons explained above, more can be observed from 1631 onwards. The most expensive offices were *escribanos de cámara y crimen* and *escribanos de provincia*, which existed only in Granada, Seville, and Valladolid. These offices were much coveted, given that they were highly profitable and had a certain social cachet, owing to their role in appeals courts. Of the offices present in every city, *regidores* were the most prized, followed by *escribanos del número*. The cheapest ones were *procuradores del número*. A more detailed analysis of the price trends is undertaken in the appendix.

III | OFFICES AS FINANCIAL ASSETS

Unlike the French literature,⁷⁵ the Spanish historiography lacks an in-depth study of the private financial uses and characteristics of offices. Such a study should first address an important puzzle: If offices could not be legally rented, how did they become prized investment assets? The decree of 19 July 1589 explicitly banned the renting of offices. Unlike the rules that forbade selling them, which became obsolete through the institutionalization process, there was no de facto legalization of office rentals in Castile.⁷⁶

Lease prohibition should have reduced the appeal of offices as investments since profits for office-holders were limited to serve the post or to pure speculation. Additionally, certain people were unable to become officers for reasons such as gender (women were under no circumstances allowed to serve in an office), age (officers had to be at least 25 years old), or location (the person in question lived far from the office's location). A quick examination of original documentation however makes it clear that hundreds of investors were willing to buy offices, even though they did not comply with such requirements.

Contemporary witnesses also suggest that offices were considered profitable investments, whether owners could serve the office or not. One of the clearest testimonies appears in *Don Quixote* by Cervantes. When the protagonist promises his fellow sufferer Sancho Panza a group of slaves as a reward, Sancho replies: 'I will sell them [the slaves] in cash, and with that money I will buy a noble title or an office with which I will be able to live a comfortable life forever'.⁷⁷ Surprisingly, Sancho, being an illiterate rustic peasant, would have been unable to exercise an office. Cervantes, who wrote the book in the heyday of the market for offices, knew this well, but also knew that anyone could make money by owning these assets. Regardless of their skills or condition, investors could use the offices as financial vehicles.

This was made possible by a contractual innovation. Similar to *censos* (the most common loan type in early modern Castile), which turned credit transactions into sale agreements to avoid the accusations of usury,⁷⁸ owners of offices exploited an analogous loophole. Proprietors could sell offices on credit, stipulating a repurchasing condition a few years after (in Spanish *pacto de retroventa*). Then, tenants (i.e. buyers) simply paid interests every year and gave back the office at the repurchasing date. Interest payments were thus equivalent to rental payments, and leases were disguised as sale transactions.

Some examples may help to clarify this process. Diego López de la Cerda inherited a solicitorship from his father on 23 July 1658.⁷⁹ Only a month later he sold the office on credit to Cristóbal Lozano at 15 400 reals.⁸⁰ The sale contract included a repurchasing agreement in the following year. Lozano only paid the interests on the loan (770 reals or 5 per cent) and returned the office

⁷⁵ Doyle, *Venality*; Pinsard and Tadjeddine, 'The marketization of the French public finance'; Descimon, 'Au XVIIe Siècle, l'office de La Chambre Des Comptes'.

⁷⁶ It must be emphasized that a few offices were exceptionally rented through judicial authorization in the second half of the seventeenth century. Such authorization was usually granted as means to pay the interests of loans secured by the office itself (Gómez-Blanco, 'When safety becomes risky', p. 90). In the eighteenth century, rental of offices appears to be common (Hernández Benítez, 'Cuando el poder se vende'). This period is, however, beyond the scope of the present research.

⁷⁷ Cervantes Saavedra, *Don Quixote* (J. Ormsby, trans.), p. 473.

⁷⁸ Quiroz, 'Reassessing the role of credit', p. 197.

⁷⁹ AGS, CCA, file 2387.

⁸⁰ AGS, CCA, file 2388.

FIGURE 3 Lease of an office. *Source:* AGS, CCA, file 2388.

at the repurchasing date (figure 3). Afterwards, Diego López repeated the same transaction with another person, Joseph de Bostelman, on 3 November 1659.⁸¹ López once again recovered the office in 1660 and ‘sold’ the office on credit to another person (Francisco Cavallero), obtaining a new *censo* of 15 400 reals for the third time in a three-year period.⁸² It is obvious that Diego López was actually leasing the office yearly.

This was not an isolated case. By contrast, the database includes 315 leases, mostly using this procedure. Table 3 displays the main features of lease contracts. As shown, leases of solicitorship and notaryship were more frequent. This sort of transaction was a good alternative for women, who could not serve the office but were able to own the assets. The female lessor indicator shows the percentage of leases which were undertaken by women. Remarkably, this condition holds good for almost half of the aldermanship leases. There were also some institutional lessors, mainly religious organizations (convents, hospitals, and confraternities). The lease duration ranged from 1 to 10 years, the average being around 3 years. Finally, the average rental price, as measured by the interest rate on the *censo*, was almost systematically 5 per cent. This is because the legal interest rate was fixed there from 1608 onwards, and most transactions took place afterwards.⁸³

In addition to office leases, the combination of repurchasing agreements, *censo*s, and offices opened the way to other financial vehicles, such as office-backed *censo*s (OBCs) and repo transactions. OBCs formed a group of mortgages (*censo*s) collateralized by an office. These assets could be traded in a secondary market. The way that OBCs worked was to buy an office; then create one or several non-redeemable *censo*s, which were backed by the office; and resell the office with the *censo*s attached. This process could be repeated several times by different investors. Indeed, the dataset contains offices that backed up to 13 different *censo*s belonging to various individuals and religious institutions.⁸⁴ As a rule, offices backed on average between three and six *censo*s. OBCs increased the marketability of offices because they allowed the property to be divided into tranches and traded.⁸⁵

⁸¹ AGS, CCA, file 2398.

⁸² AGS, CCA, file 2399.

⁸³ Ballester Martínez, ‘Los censos’, p. 39.

⁸⁴ AGS, CCA, file 2545.

⁸⁵ Quinn and Turner, *Boom and bust*.

TABLE 3 Statistics on leases of offices in Castile, 1543–1714.

Office	Number of cases	Female lessor (%)	Institutional lessor (%)	Year of first case	Minimum duration (years)	Maximum duration (years)	Average duration (years)	Minimum rental payment (%)	Maximum rental payment (%)	Average rental payment (interest rate) (%)
Aldermanship	45	40	2	1622	2	8	3.6	5	5	5.0
Solicitorship	174	33	6	1616	1	10	2.9	2	5	5.0
Notary of the number	57	39	7	1641	1	9	2.7	4	5	4.9
Other clerks	39	41	23	1588	1	4	2.1	5	13	6.0
Total	315	35	8		1	10	2.9	2	13	5.0

Note: Not all leases provided detailed information. These statistics have been computed using only documents with complete data. The rental payment of 13% is probably an error by the notary who wrote the contract. Only one observation out of 315 had an interest rate over 5%. *Source:* Author's database from AGS, CCA, Renuncias, legajos from 2295 to 2552 and AHN, Consejos, legajos from 13 745 to 13 806.

FIGURE 4 Office-backed *censos* (OBC). Source: AGS, CCA, file 2452.

Figure 4 shows an example. Juan de Castro y Zorrilla, who had cash and possibly wanted to invest in a long-term financial product, bought a solicitorship from Juan Jaime de Anaya at 23 340 reals in 1675 (7810 reals in cash and 15 620 reals in *censos*). Then, Juan de Castro created a new *censo* of 1980 reals and sold the office with all its *censos* to Gaspar de Perea at 24 200 reals (6600 reals in cash and 17 600 reals on *censos*).⁸⁶ Henceforth, Juan de Castro could have held the ownership of the new *censo*, thus receiving the annual interest payments (99 reals), or he could have sold the *censo* to another investor. If he had maintained the *censo* indefinitely, the effective annual return for Juan de Castro would have been approximately 8.18 per cent because capital gains were added to the interests of the *censo*. This transaction hence allowed him to gain a higher yield than the maximum legal interest (5 per cent).

Another sort of financial vehicle was the repo transaction. Today a repurchase agreement (repo) is the same as this product (i.e. a short-term loan secured by an asset). Office repos involved the same elements as the above-mentioned leases, but here the repurchasing date matured in the short run, and at least some portion of the principal was paid in cash. An example is shown in figure 5. Antonio Quevedo, a solicitor who had bought his office in Granada scarcely a year ago at 3300 reals (1100 in cash and 2200 on a *censo*) possibly felt a great need for liquidity in 1702. He then decided to sell his office, stipulating a repurchasing agreement to be settled 135 days later. Felipe Varela, the lender, paid him 3300 reals and received the office as collateral for the short-term loan. On the agreed date, 8 June 1702, Quevedo paid back 4400 reals to Varela and recovered the office.⁸⁷ Unfortunately, except for the given example, it is not possible to confirm that the other operations were repos since there is no proof that an interest rate was charged. Both sales had the same prices, so the same amounts of money were apparently exchanged. *Pactos de retroventa* indeed had to be exchanged a priori for the same amounts by law, although in the case of figure 5, it was different for no apparent reason.

The database includes 13 potential repos that took place in Málaga and Granada between 1658 and 1702 affecting the notary of the number and solicitor offices.⁸⁸ All these operations followed the same procedure illustrated in figure 5 with the only exception being the amounts exchanged.

⁸⁶ AGS, CCA, file 2452 and 2455.

⁸⁷ AHN, CON files 13747 and 13748.

⁸⁸ AGS, CCA, files 2395, 2387, 2397, 2437, 2430, 2440, 2446, 2449, 2450, 2460, 2481, 2482, 2533 and 2539.

FIGURE 5 Repo transaction of offices. Source: AHN, CON, file 13748/38 and 13750/38.

Interestingly, repurchasing dates in these operations always matured at exact periods such as 45, 60, 90, 120, or 135 days. It is hard to believe that such short periods allowed the parties to make any kind of profit but a financial one. Therefore, they have been considered repos, assuming that an implicit interest rate possibly existed, even though no conclusive evidence appears in the contracts. The hidden interest rate might be charged if the money initially lent was less than it stipulated in the agreement. The lender would thus ensure his profits in the formalization of the contract.

Finally, it is worth noting that offices were deeply appealing for other reasons than profitability. For instance, the upper classes were preoccupied with leaving an enduring legacy. As a result, some extremely rigid forms of ownership succeeded during the early modern period, like *mayorazgos* and *capellanías* (chantries).⁸⁹ These institutions limited owner's rights (e.g. it was not theoretically possible to sell or divide the incorporated properties in a *mayorazgo*). Since these institutions often lasted for several decades or might last for centuries, assets with low physical depreciation were required, such as real estate and land.⁹⁰ Offices were suitable assets for this motive (low depreciation) and others (e.g. they conferred high prestige). Therefore, it is common to find offices that were part of chantries and *mayorazgos*, overwhelmingly offices of aldermen.⁹¹

IV | OFFICES AS SAFE ASSETS

The financial operations shown make it clear that offices played a crucial role as collateral. Next, this section demonstrates that this role was due to several traits meant to make offices secure

⁸⁹ Chantries were religious institutions which included some assets to generate an income that would be paid to a priest for saying masses (Arroyo Vozmediano, *El ojo de la aguja*). A *mayorazgo* was a civil law institution that regulated the hereditary system in early modern Castile, preventing the entailed assets of a family from division and alienation (Clavero, *Mayorazgo y propiedad feudal*).

⁹⁰ Clavero, *Mayorazgo y propiedad feudal*.

⁹¹ The dataset contains 169 resignations of offices which were incorporated into a *mayorazgo*. Of these, 150 were *regidores* or *veinticuatro*s since these offices were more commonly owned by noblemen.

investments. The first of them concerns information. According to Hoffman et al., ‘information rather than price served to allocate resources’ in early modern financial markets,⁹² and offices stand out for being highly information insensitive. This attribute derives from a number of intrinsic qualities. First, offices were present in everyday life, and everybody was acquainted with them, especially the upper echelons who were the potential investors. Being familiar with an asset makes it easier to understand. Additionally, office yields as financial investments were quite stable, overcoming the return variability problems that might have increased uncertainty and made asset pricing harder.⁹³ Contemporaries indeed knew that leases of offices almost systematically offered returns on capital equal to 5 per cent, as shown above. For this reason, the tax on office transactions created in 1631 (*media annata de mercedes*) estimated at 5 per cent the standard office return.⁹⁴

Second, office dealings rarely suffered from adverse selection. As Akerlof’s seminal paper demonstrates, this asymmetric information problem arises because buyers know less about the hidden features of traded assets than sellers do.⁹⁵ This situation was, however, implausible in the market for offices.

Offices were intangible assets, so they did not physically depreciate and their useful life was indefinite. This fact precluded them from suffering from unobservable deterioration, which is a common source of private information. Moreover, most relevant characteristics of offices (e.g. powers and salaries) were detailed in the title, which could be requested for not only the seller but the Crown too. Local notaries were also able to provide information on some key details, such as debts on offices. This was of the utmost importance given the extent of debt in office transactions. Unlike in France, where attempts to create a mortgage registry failed,⁹⁶ from the 1590s onwards Philip II established notaries specialized in recording loans and mortgages (*escribanos del registro de censos*) in ‘every city, town, and place of the kingdom’.⁹⁷ These notaries increased transparency and efficiency in controlling for debts, reducing information cost and avoiding the risk of accepting over-mortgaged offices.⁹⁸

Overall, sellers could barely hide private information about relevant characteristics of offices. The Crown and notaries moreover acted as screening agencies, making a problem of asymmetric information unlikely.

Although adverse selection is hard to demonstrate empirically, especially in early modern markets where data are scarce, public auctions may offer some insights. Under certain conditions, auction outcomes converge with the theoretically perfect competition result, even if bidders have partial information.⁹⁹ In addition, auctions in Castile followed the English procedure. This setting may have mitigated the potential effects of adverse selection through common value.¹⁰⁰

⁹² Hoffman, Postel-Vinay, and Rosenthal, ‘What do notaries do?’, p. 504.

⁹³ An in-depth discussion about office returns is provided by Gómez-Blanco, ‘When safety becomes risky’.

⁹⁴ AHN, CON, book 545.

⁹⁵ Akerlof, ‘The market for “lemons”’.

⁹⁶ Bien, ‘Les offices, les corps, et le crédit d’état’.

⁹⁷ AGS, Consejo y Juntas de Hacienda (CJH), book 373.

⁹⁸ Hoffman, Postel-Vinay, and Rosenthal, ‘What do notaries do?’; Hoffman, Postel-Vinay, and Rosenthal, ‘Information and economic history’.

⁹⁹ Klemperer, ‘Auction theory’; Milgrom and Weber, ‘A theory of auctions’.

¹⁰⁰ In English auctions, information is transmitted in real-time among bidders, generating common value (Bulow and Klemperer, ‘Why do sellers (usually) prefer auctions?’).

FIGURE 6 Pairs of identical offices sold through both the market and public auction. *Notes:* The sales were distributed as follows: 31 were aldermanships, 21 notaries of the number, 37 solicitorships, and 3 law court clerks. *Source:* AGS, CCA, *Renuncias, legajos* from 2295 to 2552, and AHN, *Consejos, legajos* from 13745 to 13806.

Most importantly, the Castilian auctions of secondary office sales were carried out by local public authorities (and not by the private owners).¹⁰¹ The authorities acted as third-party verification, thus preventing sellers from hiding the possible negative features of the offices (e.g. debts). Then, if the adverse selection occurred in office sales, public auctions should have lessened the negative effects. A significant difference between the market and the auction price could hence be indicative of adverse selection problems. A comparative analysis of both sorts of sale is shown below. All the pairs of identical offices sold at the same time through both the market and public auctions have been identified in the database.¹⁰² Figure 6 displays the collected pairs (102 couples). Auction prices seem to be neither overvalued nor undervalued when compared with market prices. The linear trend is indeed nearly the same as the 90-degree line, which indicates that both prices are, on average, equivalent.

A paired sample *t*-test is used to complement this visual analysis. This test confirms that auction prices are not statistically different from market prices (*p*-value is 0.166; see table A4 in the appendix). This result underpins the statement that the market for offices had no substantial adverse selection problem.

A second relevant feature of safe assets is their ‘moneyness’. This concept is used synonymously with liquidity. Contemporary testimonies show a widespread wish to invest in offices. In 1581, for instance, the *corregidores* of most cities informed Philip II that several people were ‘ready to purchase offices in their jurisdictions’.¹⁰³ Similarly, the afore-mentioned Castillo de Bobadilla

¹⁰¹ Most of the public auctions in the database were secondary sales. They mostly comprised foreclosure sales (i.e. the owners of the collateral attached to an office requested it) or auctions requested by the heirs of an office-holder who had passed away.

¹⁰² ‘Almost at the same time’ means within 6 months. ‘Pairs of identical offices’ refers to offices from the same city that had the same attributes (salaries, powers, etc.).

¹⁰³ AGS, DGT, Inventory 24.

stated that investors were willing to sell all their properties or borrow remarkable amounts of money to buy an office of *regidor* in the 1590s.¹⁰⁴

These commentaries point out an office market landscape that was very similar to the *juros* market. According to Alonso García, everybody in the sixteenth century wished to acquire *juros*.¹⁰⁵ The market for offices in fact represented 59 per cent and 81 per cent of the market for *juros de alcabalas* in Burgos and Murcia, respectively, in 1640, so their sizes were comparable.¹⁰⁶ Both markets also grew rapidly in the early modern period, and market growth is often correlated with high liquidity. The market size for offices at current prices in the cities represented in the *Cortes* doubled from 1581 to 1599, and once again from 1600 to 1640.¹⁰⁷

One of the clearest signs of office liquidity was probably that the king's bankers accepted these assets as collateral and as reimbursement of their loans. Offices represented 11.91 per cent of total repayments of *asientos* in 1639–40, while silver repayments accounted for 13.63 per cent.¹⁰⁸ The use of offices to pay back debts involved not only the king and his bankers, but it was also usual among ordinary people. The *facultad de renunciación* explicitly allowed the use of offices to repay debts. Indeed, the database shows that this method was frequently used. Pedro de Salamanca, for example, paid back a debt of 11 000 reals held by *doña* María de Idiago in 1684. To do so, Pedro gave his solicitorship from Zamora (priced at 8000 reals) to *doña* María who canceled the debt and accepted the loss of 3000 reals.¹⁰⁹ Institutional investors also employed this method of debt cancellation. The Council of the Indies gave an aldermanship from Madrid to Gaspar de Prado to compensate him for the seizure of 20 460 reals of silver from America.¹¹⁰

Another insight into the liquidity was the ease of finding purchasers. Owners could sometimes lease or sell offices even before they got them. Such was the case with *doña* María de Noriega, who made an agreement with Juan de Letona to trade a solicitorship at 6600 reals on 4 March 1637. Nevertheless, María de Noriega did not inherit the office until her husband's death on 25 January 1638.¹¹¹ Similar cases often occurred in Castile during the seventeenth century.

Using the data available, it is also possible to provide some quantitative evidence of market liquidity. In particular, a yearly office turnover (i.e. the average percentage of annual transactions out of total asset stock) can be estimated. Figure 7 displays the turnover between 1631 and 1701 using resignations between non-relatives as a proxy for total sales.¹¹² The figures range between 1 per cent and 12 per cent, although they vary greatly in the cities and sorts of offices represented. The market for solicitorship was more liquid, showing a two-fold share (7 per cent) of aldermanship and notaryship (3 per cent). Unfortunately, no turnover ratio has been estimated

¹⁰⁴ Castillo de Bobadilla, *Politica para corregidores*, p. 231.

¹⁰⁵ Alonso García and Caselli, 'Government debts and financial markets in Castile'.

¹⁰⁶ Gómez-Blanco, 'When safety becomes risky', pp. 69–73.

¹⁰⁷ Gómez-Blanco, 'When safety becomes risky'.

¹⁰⁸ Sanz Ayán, *Los banqueros y la crisis*, pp. 121–45.

¹⁰⁹ AGS, CCA, REN, file 2491.

¹¹⁰ AGS, CCA, REL, file 20.

¹¹¹ AGS, CCA, REN, file 2423 and AHPV, file 1903.

¹¹² The period was limited to 1631–1701 to avoid biases caused by misreporting of resignations before 1631 and the War of Succession (1701–14). Resignations among relatives were excluded to avoid potential free appointments. Madrid was also excluded because resignations were not gathered in this city. The maximum stock of offices was selected in each city.

FIGURE 7 Turnover ratios of aldermanship, notaryship, and solicitorship markets, 1543–1714. *Notes:* Only resignations between non-relatives were included to avoid potential non-sales. *Source:* AGS, CCA, *Renuncias, legajos* from 2295 to 2552, and AHN, *Consejos, legajos* from 13745 to 13806.

for other assets in early modern Castile (not even for *juros*). It is hence impossible to carry out a comparison between these figures and other assets at the time, though it seems clear that the offices were liquid assets since the estimates are equivalent to current turnover ratios of housing markets in Europe.¹¹³

To conclude, we analyse probably the most striking characteristic of haven assets, that is, their higher value during adverse economic times. This feature, also known as the β negative condition, allows us to empirically test for the financial safety of a specific asset. To make the analysis we run some hedonic price models. These models not only assess the effect of intrinsic characteristics of offices on their pricing but also deal with the relationship between office prices and some proxies for economic and financial stress.

The appendix shows the definitions and main statistics of the variables included in the models. In short, the panel data consist of 16 cross-sectional units (i.e. a specific office from a city) over 133 years. Only offices existing in all cities are included. Except for *perpetuación*, which has some missing values, the rest of the variables exhibit 2128 observations. The dependent variable is the yearly mean price of an office in current reals. Note that only the sales of offices are considered since no information about prices was found in the other resignations.¹¹⁴ Among the regressors, some qualities of offices were taken into consideration, such as *perpetuaciones* and

¹¹³ Turnover ratios of European housing markets between 1999 and 2013 ranged from 1% to 8% (Dröes and Francke, ‘What causes the positive price-turnover correlation?’, p. 628).

¹¹⁴ The number of observations is higher than the total number of sales in the database because prices in some years were imputed to have a balanced panel data. Exponential interpolation was applied in these cases.

special faculties (or licenses).¹¹⁵ Additionally, proxies for economic growth (GDP per capita), monetary problems (inflation and silver premium), and public debt risk (*juros* structural break) were included.

Given the characteristics of the database, such as its large T and possible nonstationary variables, certain models (e.g. the fixed effect model) can yield biased results. Therefore, I test for unit roots by using Im–Pesaran–Shin, Breitung, and Breitung and Das tests.¹¹⁶ All the tests show that price, GDPs, and the three-year moving average regional consumer price index (Cpi3ma) have a unit root in all panels. The panels of these variables are in fact cointegrated.¹¹⁷

In these circumstances, panel dynamic models are preferable. Given that cross-unit effects are likely heterogeneous and cross-sectional independence is invalidated,¹¹⁸ augmented mean group is particularly the most appropriate estimator.¹¹⁹ This methodology can specifically deal with cross-sectional data dependence, serially uncorrelated errors, nonstationary, and heterogeneous cross-sectional unit effects.¹²⁰ Moreover, it helps in solving some problems that arise from mis-specifying the functional form since it includes unobserved common processes that vary across cross-sectional units capturing the effect of non-included relevant variables.

AMG estimator proceeds in two stages. The specification of the first stage is:

$$\Delta P_{it} = b_1 \Delta \text{Perpetuación}_{it} + b_2 \Delta \text{Specialfaculty}_{it} + b_3 \Delta \text{GDPs}_{it} + b_4 \Delta \text{Cpi3ma}_{it} + b_5 \Delta \text{Silverpremium}_{it} + b_6 \Delta \text{Jurosbreak}_{it} + \sum_{t=2}^T y \Delta \text{YEAR}_t + e_{it} \quad (1)$$

where P_{it} is the dependent variable for price of office i at year t , and Perpetuación_{it} and $\text{Specialfaculty}_{it}$ are dummy variables equal to one if the office is perpetual or has a special license. GDPs_{it} is the GDP per capita estimated by Prados et al.¹²¹ Cpi3ma_{it} is the three-year moving average regional consumer price index (CPI). Both the Cpi3ma_{it} and $\text{Silverpremium}_{it}$ are provided by Hamilton.¹²² Jurosbreak_{it} is a dummy that represents the structural break in *juros* from 1593 onwards. Finally, b_j are the parameters, and e_{it} is the residual.

From this step, which uses a standard first differences ordinary least squares (FDOLS) regression,¹²³ year dummy parameters (γ_t) are estimated. Then, the dummies are included in the second

¹¹⁵ Offices could have several special faculties. However, this variable takes into consideration only the following ones: the right to appoint a deputy (for non-perpetual offices), to be able to access city hall with a cape and weapons, electability as *procurador de Cortes* or *fiel ejecutor* (for *regidores-veinticuatro*s), and to serve another office simultaneously.

¹¹⁶ Im, Pesaran, and Shin, ‘Testing for unit roots’; Breitung, ‘The local power of some unit root tests’; Breitung and Das, ‘Panel unit root tests’.

¹¹⁷ Pedroni, ‘Panel cointegration’; Kao, ‘Spurious regression’; Westerlund, ‘New simple tests’.

¹¹⁸ The null hypothesis of cross-sectional independence is rejected at 99% of confidence by using Pesaran ‘General diagnostic tests’; *idem*, ‘Testing weak cross-sectional dependence’.

¹¹⁹ Eberhardt and Teal, ‘Econometrics for grumblers’.

¹²⁰ Eberhardt, Helmers, and Strauss, ‘Do spillovers matter’.

¹²¹ Prados de la Escosura, Álvarez-Nogal, and Santiago-Caballero, ‘Growth recurring in preindustrial Spain?’.

¹²² Hamilton, *American treasure*; *idem*, *War and prices in Spain*.

¹²³ City and office dummies cannot be included in this specification.

TABLE 4 Benchmark estimations.

Variables	(1) AMG	(2) AMG std	(3) AMG	(4) AMG
Perpetuacion	5282* (3123)	0.331 (0.217)		285.9 (2332)
Specialfaculty	2283 (3186)	0.194 (0.154)	3872 (2502)	1256 (1708)
GDPs	-582.2*** (136.7)	-0.381*** (0.0531)	-646.8*** (137.8)	-670.6*** (139.9)
Cpi3ma	122.6 (96.05)	0.159 (0.132)	70.03 (118.3)	45.67 (144.3)
Silverpremium	45.34 (48.56)	0.0179 (0.0977)	60.98 (55.49)	2.130 (50.97)
Jurosbreak	6055** (2967)	0.644*** (0.224)	6170* (3331)	3512 (2940)
Trend	-45.54 (94.68)	-0.00950** (0.00417)	-1.625 (112.0)	-172.4** (85.50)
c_d_p				0.779*** (0.264)
Constant	61 712*** (14 600)	-0.0894 (0.187)	69 758*** (15 027)	75 577*** (17 435)
Observations	1849	1849	2128	1849
Number of panel units	16	16	16	16
Group trend	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
CDP	No	No	No	Yes

Notes: Standard errors are in parentheses. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$.

stage, which has the following form:

$$P_{it} = a_i + b_1 \text{Perpetuación}_{it} + b_2 \text{Specialfaculty}_{it} + b_3 \text{GDPs}_{it} + b_4 \text{Cpi3ma}_{it} + b_5 \text{Silverpremium}_{it} + b_6 \text{Jurosbreak}_{it} + c_i t + d_i \hat{\gamma}_t + e_{it} \quad (2)$$

The second stage (in levels) contains linear trend terms ($c_i t$) by cross-sectional units.

Table 4 shows the benchmark results of AMG models. Columns 1–3 do not impose a common dynamic process with a unit coefficient, whereas Model 4 does impose it.¹²⁴ Columns 1 and 2 have the same specification, but variables have been standardized in the second one for ease of comparison.¹²⁵ Finally, column 3 excludes the variable of perpetuations to have the maximum number of observations possible (2128).

¹²⁴ When a common dynamic process is assumed, average γ_t is subtracted from the left side of Equation (2). Not applying a common dynamic process is preferred in our model.

¹²⁵ Jurosbreak and the other factor variables have not been standardized because they are dummy variables.

The results are conclusive and very similar in all the specifications. GDP has a negative and significant impact on office prices, indicating that the larger the crisis, the higher the office value. The coefficient particularly means that 1 per cent decrease in GDP per capita generates on average an increment of 582 reals (or 670.6 in Model 4) in office prices (a price increase of approximately 2 per cent). As shown in column 2, this coefficient is larger than those of the other continuous variables. A one standard deviation increase in GDPs reduces 0.38 standard deviations of office prices.

The Jurosbreak coefficient is also significant, positive, and large (6055 reals in Model 1 or 0.64 standard deviations), if common dynamic process is not applied. The positive coefficient shows that the credibility problems of *juros* increased the demand for offices after 1593.¹²⁶ In particular, the price of an office increases on average by 17 per cent when *juros* face difficulties. A plausible cause could have been that investors substituted *juros* for offices in the 1590s. Some scholars have qualitatively inferred this substitution effect. A perfect example is provided by Pinedo Gómez who points out that Diego de las Cuevas, who had invested in *juros* in the early 1590s, acquired 31 notaryships from different towns between 1596 and 1602 to resell them in the following years.¹²⁷ Ruiz Martín also highlights that from 1593 onwards Castilian investors switched their preferences from bonds to real assets.¹²⁸

The coefficients of CPI and silver premium are not significant, but they show the expected sign (i.e. positive). There is a similar situation with perpetuations and special faculties. Perpetuations only show a significant coefficient in column 1. However, as expected its effect is 5282 reals, representing 15 per cent of the average price, which was the most common value of these licenses in the market.¹²⁹

In the appendix, several robustness checks are carried out. For instance, alternative definitions of GDP (using the demand approach in column 1 of table A2) and *juros* flaws (establishing the critical period of bonds in 1596–1607 and 1621–1700 in column 2) are used. All these alternative models point to the same conclusions as the initial specifications.

Different methodologies are also employed. On the one hand, the group-mean panel-dynamic ordinary least squares model (PDOLS) is displayed in column 3.¹³⁰ It must be emphasized that this model assumes some conditions that are not validated by the dataset, such as cross-sectional independence. Still, the results are in line with the AMG model (GDP coefficient is significant and equal to -763). On the other hand, a random effects model (REM) and a fixed effects model (FEM) are shown in columns 4 and 5, respectively. As these methodologies are not appropriate to assess the relationship of nonstationary variables, GDP, CPI, and silver premium are excluded. By contrast, REM and FEM allow for the addition of variables that measure the impact of the type of office and city on the office price. These variables are then included. As expected, aldermen are the most appreciated offices, although the difference

¹²⁶ A negative supply shock could also explain the rise in office prices. However, this explanation is unlikely, as stock of offices did not decrease over the years in the cities analysed (i.e. no office was ‘consumed’). Additionally, a more accurate definition of *juros* flaws is used below, considering the period of 1608–20 good for *juros* credibility. This period coincided with the ‘suspension of sales’ (i.e. reduction in primary sales; Marcos Martín, ‘Las ventas de oficios en Castilla’). Even so, both specifications show similar results. Therefore, a negative supply shock hardly fits with the evidence.

¹²⁷ Pinedo Gómez, ‘La venta de escribanías’, p. 41.

¹²⁸ Ruiz Martín, *La Banca En España Hasta 1782*, p. 52.

¹²⁹ Gómez-Blanco, ‘When safety becomes risky’, p. 163.

¹³⁰ Pedroni, ‘Purchasing power parity tests’; Pedroni, ‘Panel cointegration’.

in price with notaries is small and not statistically significant.¹³¹ In regional terms, offices from Madrid are by far the most expensive ones, followed by offices from Seville. In fact, there is a premium for offices from Andalusian cities compared with those of northern Castile, probably due to the higher income of this region at the time. The *juros* break is again significant, and its coefficient is larger than in previous estimates since it captures the effect of other covariates highly correlated with bond problems that have been excluded in this specification, like GDP.

On the whole, all empirical evidence indicates that offices were information insensitive and liquid and increased their prices as economy weakened. These unique traits confirm that offices were haven assets.

V | CONCLUSIONS

This article is the first to study how public local offices in early modern Castile became private financial products and fulfilled all the conditions for being considered safe assets. To do this, I built the most comprehensive dataset thus far of the Castilian venal system covering the period between 1543 and 1714, which contained about 1910 sales and 4157 resignations of four types of office in eight major Castilian cities.

After analysing the traditional haven assets in the Castilian economy (i.e. *real de a ocho* and *juros*), I demonstrated that a financial innovation, the repurchasing agreement (in Spanish *pacto de retroventa*), allowed office investors to transform prohibited leases into legal sale transactions. A loophole was thus exploited to break the prohibition of renting offices. Moreover, the combination of repurchasing agreement, offices, and *censos* (loans) opened the way to more sophisticated financial vehicles, such as repos and office-backed *censos*. This finding explains why hundreds of investors bought offices, even though they could not serve them, making large profits other than the office fees and social promotion.

Afterwards, I showed that the offices met all the requirements of haven assets. First, they did not suffer from adverse selection. From 1543 onwards, the Crown progressively defined the property rights of offices, likely seeking to maximize their prices in future sales and laying at the same the foundation for an information insensitive asset. The information insensitivity particularly derived from their simplicity, publicly known characteristics, freedom from physical depreciation, stable yields, and screening controls (the Crown and local notaries). Second, anecdotal evidence and estimated turnover ratios show that offices were traded in liquid secondary markets.

As a final point, I used dynamic panel data models to test whether offices had higher value during worsening economic times. In particular, using an AMG model it was shown that office prices had a negative and significant relationship with GDP per capita. Problems of *juros* also had a positive impact on prices of offices from the 1590s onwards, when Castilian public debt lost credibility. These results, which are robust to different specifications, indicate that the demand for offices increased during periods of financial and economic distress.

To sum up, all the evidence analysed demonstrated that offices were safe assets in the early modern period.

¹³¹ Notaries of the number and the city of Valladolid are the reference points since these dummy variables were not included to avoid perfect multicollinearity.

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DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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